

HIPPARCOS / TYCHO

Star Mapper Optimisation

L Lindegren (1982 April 6)

Lund Observatory
Box 1107
S-22104, LUND, Sweden

SUMMARY

Analytical expressions are given for optimisation of Star Mapper slit widths for a given MTF. Preliminary results are obtained for the semi-circular aperture (320 and 270 mm $\emptyset$), and predicted mean errors are compared with numerical simulations.

THEORY

Let the SM counts $\{n_k\}$ be modelled as a Poisson process with expectation

$$\bar{n}_k = E(n_k) = b + a h(ku - p_0) \tag{1}$$

where

- b = background count level [counts/sample]
- a = stellar count level in absence of grid [counts/sample]
- p_0 = true "position" of star (at time $k = 0$, wrt slit) [rad]
- $u = v\Delta t$ = angle corresponding to the sample interval Δt [rad]
- h = single-slit response function (dimensionless).

The function $h(\cdot)$ is normalised in such a way that, for a slit of width r [rad] in the scanning direction,

$$h(0) \rightarrow 1 \quad \text{as} \quad r \rightarrow \infty, \tag{2}$$

and

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} h(\eta) d\eta = r \tag{3}$$

The position p_0 will be estimated by maximising the cross-correlation

$$C(p) = \sum_k h(ku - p) n_k \tag{4}$$

i.e., by solving for p in the equation

$$C'(p) = 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \hat{p} \quad (5)$$

By Taylor expansion we have

$$0 = C'(\hat{p}) = C'(p_0 + \hat{p} - p_0) \approx C'(p_0) + (\hat{p} - p_0) C''(p_0) \quad (6)$$

from which the estimation error is obtained as

$$p - p_0 = - \frac{C'(p_0)}{C''(p_0)} \quad (7)$$

Taking the expectation of

$$-C'(p_0) = \sum_k h'(ku - p_0) n_k \quad (8)$$

we find, by means of (1),

$$\begin{aligned} E[-C'(p_0)] &= b \sum_k h'(ku - p_0) + a \sum_k h'(ku - p_0) h(ku - p_0) \\ &\approx 0 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where we have used the approximations

$$\sum_k h'(ku - p_0) \approx \frac{1}{u} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} h'(\eta) d\eta = \frac{1}{u} [h(\eta)]_{-\infty}^{+\infty} = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_k h'(ku - p_0) h(ku - p_0) &\approx \frac{1}{u} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} h'(\eta) h(\eta) d\eta \\ &= \frac{1}{u} \left[\frac{1}{2} h^2(\eta) \right]_{-\infty}^{+\infty} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

In a similar manner we find

$$\begin{aligned} E[C''(p_0)] &= b \sum_k h''(ku - p_0) + a \sum_k h''(ku - p_0) h(ku - p_0) \\ &\approx - \frac{1}{u} Aa \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where

$$A = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} [h'(\eta)]^2 d\eta \quad [\text{rad}^{-1}] \quad (13)$$

Thus

$$\hat{p} - p_0 \approx \frac{u}{Aa} C'(p_0) \quad (14)$$

From (9) it follows that $E(\hat{p} - p_0) = 0$, i.e., $\hat{p}$ is an unbiased estimate of p_0 .

Using the Poisson property of the counts,

$$E(n_k n_\ell) = E(n_k) E(n_\ell) + \delta_{k\ell} E(n_k) \quad (15)$$

where $\delta_{k\ell}$ is the Kronecker delta, we find

$$\begin{aligned} E[C'(p_0)^2] &= \sum_k \sum_\ell h'(ku - p_0) h'(\ell u - p_0) E(n_k n_\ell) \\ &= \left[\sum_k h'(ku - p_0) E(n_k) \right]^2 + \sum_k [h'(ku - p_0)]^2 E(n_k) \\ &= b \sum_k [h'(ku - p_0)]^2 + a \sum_k [h'(ku - p_0)]^2 h(ku - p_0) \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Putting

$$B = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} [h'(\eta)]^2 h(\eta) d\eta \quad / \quad \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} [h'(\eta)]^2 d\eta \quad (17)$$

(dimensionless), we have

$$E[C'(p_0)^2] \approx \frac{A}{u} b + \frac{AB}{u} a \quad (18)$$

Combining with (12) and (14) we finally obtain the variance of p ,

$$\sigma_p^2 = E[(p - p_0)^2] \approx \frac{b + aB}{Aa^2} u \quad (19)$$

Thus the only characteristics of $h(\cdot)$ of concern are A and B given by (13) and (17). In the following we express these parameters directly in terms of the slit width (r), MTF, and sampling interval (u).

From (17) it is seen that B is the average height of $h(\cdot)$, computed with weighting factor $[h']^2$. Thus $h \approx B$ at the points of maximum slope $|h'|$, and in practice we have to a good approximation

$$B \approx 0.6 h(0) \quad (20)$$

Since $h(\cdot)$ is the convolution of the diffraction image with two rectangular functions of width u and r (for the sampling interval and slit, respectively), we find

$$h(\eta) = \frac{r}{\lambda} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \text{sinc}(\pi u y / \lambda) \text{sinc}(\pi r y / \lambda) \text{OTF}(y, \tau y) \exp(-i2\pi \eta y / \lambda) dy \quad (21)$$

where

- η = angular coordinate along scan [rad]
- λ = effective wavelength [m]
- $\text{OTF}(y, z)$ = optical transfer function (complex) for linear displacements y and z [m] along and normal to scan
- τ = $\tan(\text{slit inclination with respect to } z \text{ axis})$
- r = slit width measured along y axis [rad]

In the following we neglect phase errors and assume $\text{OTF} = \text{MTF}$ (real). Thus

$$h(0) = \frac{2r}{\lambda} \int_0^{\infty} \text{sinc}(\pi u y / \lambda) \text{sinc}(\pi r y / \lambda) \text{MTF}(y, \tau y) dy \quad (22)$$

from which B follows according to (21). By means of Parseval's theorem we also find

$$A = \frac{8 \pi^2 r^2}{\lambda^3} \int_0^{\infty} \text{sinc}^2(\pi u y / \lambda) \text{sinc}^2(\pi r y / \lambda) \text{MTF}^2(y, \tau y) y^2 dy \quad (23)$$

OPTIMISATION OF SLIT WIDTH

A transit across N identical and well separated slits will be determined with positional variance

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{1}{N} \sigma_p^2 \quad (24)$$

This shall be minimised with respect to the slit width (r). In the expression for the single-slit variance, (19), not only the numbers A and B depend on r , as given by (20), (22), and (23), but also the background count level b will depend on r , because of the sky brightness. This must also be taken into account.

For a star of blue magnitude (B-magnitude) m , the stellar count level is

$$a = \Delta t f 10^{-0.4(m-9)} \quad (25)$$

where Δt is the sampling interval [s] and f is the photoelectron flux for a star of magnitude 9 [Hz].

Let L be the vertical length (along z) of each slit [arcsec], and let r be the slit width in [arcsec], and m_{sky} the magnitude of one square arcsec sky. The background count level is

$$b = \left[2NLr'' f 10^{-0.4(m_{\text{sky}}-9)} + d \right] \Delta t \quad (26)$$

where d is the dark count rate [Hz]. Inserting into (19) we get

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{v}{NA} \frac{0.6 h(0) f 10^{-0.4(m-9)} + 2NLr'' f 10^{-0.4(m_{\text{sky}}-9)} + d}{\left[f 10^{-0.4(m-9)} \right]^2} \quad (27)$$

with v = scan rate [rad/s] and $h(0)$ and A from (22) and (23).

PROVISIONAL RESULTS

The optimisation of r has been carried out with various assumed instrument parameters and data. The most important assumptions have been summarised in Tables 1, 2, and 3.

The count rates for a 9:th magnitude star in the blue (b) or visual (v) channel, f_b and f_v , are obtained from

$$f = a_c (1 - \epsilon^2) \frac{\pi}{8} D^2 \int F_\lambda T_\lambda Q_\lambda T_{.\lambda} d\lambda \quad (28)$$

yielding (for $D = 0.32$ m)

$$f_b = 12511 \text{ Hz} \quad (29)$$

$$f_v = 11950 \text{ Hz} \quad (30)$$

The separation wavelength between b and v, 480 nm, was in fact chosen so as to give $f_b \approx f_v$ for a B-V = 0.5 star.

The effective wavelengths of the two bands, λ_b and λ_v , are

$$\lambda = \frac{\int F_\lambda T_\lambda Q_\lambda T_{.\lambda} \lambda d\lambda}{\int F_\lambda T_\lambda Q_\lambda T_{.\lambda} d\lambda} \quad (31)$$

or

$$\lambda_b = 437 \text{ nm} \quad (32)$$

$$\lambda_v = 527 \text{ nm} \quad (33)$$

Because of the relatively small bandwidth (FWHM $\approx$ 85 and 80 nm in b and v), it is sufficient to use the monochromatic approximation, eq (21), provided the appropriate effective wavelengths are inserted.

Numerical results are given in Table 4-a to 4-g.

COMMENTS TO TABLE 4

Table 4-a: Nominal instrument, $m = 10$

The optimum slit width is close to $r = 1''$. The minima in $\sigma(r)$ are always rather shallow, so any value in the range 0.7 - 1.3 arcsec seems acceptable. A wider slit will give more accurate photometry, while a narrower slit will give results less sensitive to enhanced background. Since these arguments seem to cancel each other, the value

$$r'' = 1.0 \text{ arcsec} \quad (34)$$

is provisionally adopted. The corresponding mean errors for a transit of 4 slits are

$$\sigma(b) = 0.079 \text{ arcsec} \quad (35)$$

$$\sigma(v) = 0.091 \text{ arcsec} \quad (36)$$

These are somewhat theoretical numbers and must be checked against numerical simulations (see below).

Table 4-b: Nominal instrument, $m = 9$

For $r = 1''$ the mean errors are reduced by a factor ≈ 0.53 .

Table 4-c: Nominal instrument, $m = 11$

For $r = 1''$ the mean errors are increased by a factor ≈ 2.1 .

Table 4-d: Reduced telescope diameter, $D = 0.27 \text{ m}$

The optimum slit width is increased to $r = 1.2 \text{ arcsec}$ and the mean errors are increased by a factor ≈ 1.34 .

Table 4-e: Reduced slit inclination, 26.565° ($\tau = 0.5$)

The optimum slit width is reduced to $r = 0.8 \text{ arcsec}$ and the mean errors are reduced by a factor ≈ 0.77 , but since the transit errors are effectively multiplied by $1/\tau$ when transferred to the vertical coordinate, the net effect is an error increased by ≈ 1.54 .

Table 4-f: Twice as many slits, $N = 8$

The slit width should be reduced to $r = 0.9''$. The resulting mean errors are reduced by a factor ≈ 0.84 compared to the nominal configuration.

Table 4-g: Increased sampling frequency, $1/\Delta t = 600$ Hz

The optimum slit width is still $r = 1.0''$, and the mean errors are reduced by a factor ≈ 0.98 .

SIMULATION OF TRANSITS

100 transits across the slit pattern shown in Fig. 1 were simulated and the transit positions (p) estimated by means of the linear filter and interpolation algorithm depicted in Fig. 2. An example of filter outputs is given in Fig. 3.

Only the visual (v) channel was considered, with the nominal parameters given in Table 1. The single-slit response function $h(\eta)$, computed from eq (21), is given in Table 5. For the relevant star magnitude ($m = 10$, B-V = 0.5) and sky brightness ($m_{\text{sky}} = 22.5$), we have

$$a = 11.88 \text{ counts/sample} \quad (38)$$

$$b = 3.14 \text{ counts/sample} \quad (39)$$

The true position p_0 was chosen by means of a random number generator and the expected count sequence was then obtained from

$$\bar{n}_k = b + a \sum_s h(ku - p_0 - p_s) \quad (40)$$

where p_s , $s = 1, 2, 3, 4$, are the slit positions,

$$p_1 = 0, \quad p_2 = 3.75'', \quad p_3 = 15'', \quad p_4 = 22.5'' \quad (41)$$

and $h(\eta)$ was interpolated from Table 5, with $h = 0$ for $|\eta| > 2''$.

The counting sequence $\{n_k\}$ was then generated according to the Poisson distribution and using a pseudo-random number generator, and fed through the numerical filter algorithm in Fig. 2 to yield the estimated position $\hat{p}$ and the estimation error $\hat{p} - p_0$.

Results:

The distribution of estimation errors, $\hat{p} - p_0$, is shown in Fig. 4. The mean and rms values are

$$\langle (\hat{p} - p_0) \rangle = -0.005 \text{ arcsec} \quad (42)$$

$$(\hat{p} - p_0)_{\text{rms}} = 0.101 \text{ arcsec} \quad (43)$$

The latter value should be compared to the theoretical $\sigma = 0.091$ arcsec from Table 4-a.

The photometric precision was estimated from the distribution of the extreme values of the filter output (R_k). From the response function $h(\cdot)$ and the filter coefficients as given in Fig. 2, one derives the relation

$$\hat{a} = 0.001450 (R_k)_{\max} \quad (44)$$

We find

$$\langle \hat{a} \rangle = 11.77 \text{ counts/sample} \quad (45)$$

$$(\hat{a} - \langle \hat{a} \rangle)_{\text{rms}} = 1.78 \text{ counts/sample} \quad (46)$$

corresponding to a mean error of 0.164 magnitudes per transit.

COMPARISON WITH THE OPTIMUM ESTIMATOR

It is known that estimating the signal parameters (b , a , p_0) in a rigorous way, e.g. by maximum likelihood, results in non-linear equations. In particular, the equivalent filter for p_0 has coefficients depending on the ratio a/b .

Therefore, the present linear filter cannot be optimal, at least not for more than a specific value of a/b . As an indication of the quality of the present filter, it is useful to compare with a hypothetical optimum estimator, for which the Cramér-Rao bound is virtually reached:

$$\sigma_{\text{opt}}^2 = \left[N \sum_k \frac{[a h'(ku)]^2}{b + a h(ku)} \right]^{-1} \quad (47)$$

With $a = 11.88$ ($m = 10$), $b = 3.14$, $N = 4$, $u = 0.375$ arcsec, and $h(\cdot)$ from Table 5, we find

$$\sigma_{\text{opt}} = 0.088 \text{ arcsec} \quad (48)$$

to be compared with $\sigma = 0.091$ from eq (27) and 0.101 arcsec from the numerical experiments.

The filter coefficients (1,2,5,9,12,9,5,2,1) used in the simulations were chosen to be roughly proportional to $h(ku)$ for $k = -4$ to 4. This is in fact close to the optimum linear filter for the very faint stars ($a/b \ll 1$). In practice, the faintest observable stars rather correspond to $(a/b) \approx 1$ or 1.5 ($m = 11.4$ to 11.0 for $m_{\text{sky}} = 22.5$). To approximate the maximum likelihood estimator for any given ratio (a/b), the filter coefficients should in fact be proportional to

$$\frac{h(ku)}{1 + (a/b) h(ku)} \quad (49)$$

Thus the coefficients (1,2,4,6,7,6,4,2,1) should be slightly better than the ones used in the simulations.

COMPUTATIONAL CONSIDERATIONS: SIMPLIFIED ON-BOARD ALGORITHM

Application of the linear filter in Fig. 2 requires 20 additions and 6 multiplications per sample, plus comparisons and interpolation to each transit. If the a priori uncertainty of the transit is 1.5" (star position error plus real-time attitude error), then it will be necessary to process a stretch of data corresponding to $\pm 4.5''$ around the expected transit, or 25 consecutive values of R_k (at 400 Hz sampling frequency). Thus the total computational load for one such transit is of the order of 600 additions and 200 multiplications, plus a non-negligible storage (some 400 bytes).

This is acceptable for the a posteriori attitude determination (and TYCHO), but for the real-time attitude determination, where the required transit accuracy is much relaxed, one can use a computationally much simpler algorithm.

Firstly, if only the position is estimated (and not the star brightness), a balanced filter is not required; in fact, background subtraction only adds unnecessary noise in this case. Thus, the position estimator can work directly on Q_k rather than $9Q_k - 4q_k$, which means fewer additions and less storage (see Fig. 2). Secondly, the 9-point smoother (1,2,5,9,12,9,5,2,1) can be replaced e.g. by a 2-point moving average (1,1). If this is implemented before the matched filter, it will simply mean a reduced sampling rate (200 Hz). The resulting algorithm is then as follows.

If n_k is the sample obtained when the star is expected to be 4.5" in front of the first slit (Fig. 1), then start computing:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} A(1) &= n(k) + n(k+1) \\ A(2) &= n(k+2) + n(k+3) \\ &\vdots \\ A(43) &= n(k+84) + n(k+85) \end{aligned} \right\} \begin{array}{l} \text{N.B.: } A(19) \text{ and } A(20) \\ \text{are not computed} \\ \text{(82 additions)} \end{array} \quad (50)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} B(1) &= A(1) + A(6) + A(21) + A(31) \\ B(2) &= A(2) + A(7) + A(22) + A(32) \\ &\vdots \\ B(13) &= A(13) + A(18) + A(33) + A(43) \end{aligned} \right\} \begin{array}{l} \text{(39 additions)} \\ \end{array} \quad (51)$$

Then if $B(\ell)$ is the highest point and $2 \leq \ell \leq 12$, compute

$$\hat{p} = \text{const} + u \left[k + 2\ell + \frac{B(\ell+1) - B(\ell-1)}{2B(\ell) - B(\ell+1) - B(\ell-1)} \right] \quad (52)$$

This requires some 150 additions and a few multiplications and divisions per transit, and data storage of some 100 bytes. The 82 additions in (50) can be avoided by means of a separate count accumulating register sampled at half the normal sampling rate.

Examination of the 100 transit simulations reported above indicates that the rms positional error is about 0.20", compared to 0.10" for the more elaborate algorithm in Fig. 2.

CONCLUSIONS AND THE PROPOSED CONFIGURATION

From this study it appears that $N = 4$ slits give sufficient (~ 0.1) accuracy for transits of stars with $m \leq 10$. Using more slits will not give drastically improved performance due to the sky background. The simple non-periodic pattern in Fig. 1 effectively eliminates slit ambiguity both for the on-board processing and (above all) for the TYCHO reductions.

The proposed slit configuration is shown in Fig. 5. Each Star Mapper field contains two groups of slits inclined at $\tau = \pm 1$. The absence of a vertical ($\tau = 0$) group is no disadvantage since one transit at each of the two groups determine the attitude around two perpendicular axes, as required. The two slit groups should be separated by a small distance (20 arcsec in Fig. 5) to avoid confusion of transits near the symmetry line ($\zeta = 0$).

In order to avoid switching mirrors, dichroic mirrors could be used to separate the blue (b) and visual (v) wavelength bands (Fig. 6). This has a further quite important advantage: if the operating PMT's use the same grid (e.g. b_1 and v_1 in Fig. 6), then the signals from the two PMT's can be added to improve the signal-to-noise ratio by a factor $\sqrt{2}$ for the determination of positions (while the two channels must of course be kept separated for the photometric purpose of TYCHO). Although this mode of operation is preferred it is of course still possible to use a combination v_1 and b_2 , for instance, if two PMT's should fail.

Table 1. Nominal and alternative values for some parameters

Designation	Explanation	Nominal value	Alternative value(s)
m_{sky}	sky brightness per arcsec ²	22.5	21.5
m	stellar (B) magnitude	10	9, 11
B-V	star colour	0.5	-
D	telescope aperture diameter	0.32 m	0.27 m
ϵ	linear obstruction ratio	0.4	-
T_{λ}, Q_{λ}	transmittance, quantum eff.	Table 2	-
$\arctan(\tau)$	SM slit inclination	45°	26.565°
N	number of slits per SM	4	8
L	length (along z) of each slit	2400"	-
r"	slit width (along y)	0.1 - 2"	-
v	scan rate	150"/s	-
Δt	sampling period	1/400 s	1/600 s
a_c	discriminator counting eff.	0.8	-
d	dark count rate	300 Hz	-

Table 2. Derivation of photoelectron rates

λ = wavelength [nm]
 F_{λ} = photon flux for B = 9 star, B-V = 0.5 [$\text{Hz m}^{-2} \text{nm}^{-1}$]
 T_{λ} = instrument transmittance (excluding filters)
 Q_{λ} = quantum efficiency (Super S-11)
 $T_{b\lambda}$ = filter transmittance for "blue" channel
 $T_{v\lambda}$ = filter transmittance for "visual" channel
 $f_{b, v}$ = count rate for B = 9 star, without grid [Hz]

λ	F_{λ}	T_{λ}	Q_{λ}	$T_{b\lambda}$	$T_{v\lambda}$	$FTQT_b$	$FTQT_v$
350	24741	.0000	.23	.90	.00	0	0
375	28988	.0945	.23	.90	.00	567	0
400	32759	.5159	.23	.90	.00	3498	0
425	35973	.6552	.23	.90	.00	4879	0
450	38603	.7304	.22	.90	.00	5583	0
475	40660	.7826	.20	.63	.27	4009	1718
500	42180	.8184	.17	.00	.90	0	5282
525	43214	.8460	.14	.00	.90	0	4606
550	43819	.8645	.10	.00	.90	0	3409
575	44053	.8648	.04	.00	.90	0	1371
600	43974	.8463	.03	.00	.90	0	1005
625	43634	.7998	.01	.00	.90	0	314
650	43082	.7520	.00	.00	.90	0	0

Sources:

- F_{λ} and T_{λ} are from the note by P Hollier, 1981 Dec 04 (HIP/PH/VL/0250.81), Signal Model for Instrumental ...
- Q_{λ} from EMI data sheet (typical response curve for 2 in tubes)
- $T_{b\lambda}$, $T_{v\lambda}$ are assumed curves, corresponding to a dichroic splitting mirror with separation wavelength 480 nm

Table 3. Diffraction-limited (MTF_0) and assumed (MTF) modulation transfer function.

Y [m]	26.565° incl. ($\tau = 0.5$)			45.000° incl. ($\tau = 1.0$)		
	MTF_0	MTF	MTF/MTF_0	MTF_0	MTF	MTF/MTF_0
.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
.01	.91	.89	.98	.87	.83	.96
.02	.83	.80	.96	.76	.70	.92
.03	.75	.70	.94	.66	.58	.88
.04	.67	.62	.92	.55	.46	.84
.05	.59	.53	.90	.46	.37	.80
.06	.53	.47	.88	.37	.30	.80
.07	.51	.43	.86	.31	.24	.80
.08	.43	.36	.84	.24	.19	.80
.09	.38	.31	.82	.20	.16	.80
.10	.32	.25	.80	.18	.14	.80
.11	.30	.24	.80	.14	.11	.80
.12	.28	.22	.80	.10	.08	.80
.13	.26	.21	.80	.07	.06	.80
.14	.23	.18	.80	.04	.03	.80
.15	.21	.17	.80	.02	.01	.80
.16	.19	.15	.80	.00	.00	-
.17	.16	.13	.80	.00	.00	-
.18	.13	.10	.80	.00	.00	-
.19	.10	.08	.80	.00	.00	-
.20	.08	.06	.80	.00	.00	-
.21	.05	.04	.80	.00	.00	-
.22	.02	.02	.80	.00	.00	-
.23	.01	.01	.80	.00	.00	-
.24	.00	.00	-	.00	.00	-

Note: MTF_0 is for a semi-circular aperture of diameter $D = 0.32$ m and obstruction ratio $\epsilon = 0.4$. The degradation factors MTF/MTF_0 are quite arbitrary.

RUN
TAU, 1/DT, N, M, D?1,400,4,10,.32

TAU = 1
1/DT = 400
N = 4
M = 10
D = .32

TABLE 4-A

NOMINAL INSTRUMENT M = 10

R	HD	A	L =	
			S(22.5)	S(21.5)
			4.37000E-07	
			(σ for $m_{sky} = 22.5$)	(σ for $m_{sky} = 21.5$)
.1	9.74780E-02	4735.34	.212676	.233991
.2	.192276	18070.4	.135614	.152908
.3	.281957	37686.1	.108752	.124161
.4	.36454	60561.6	9.55125E-02	.110002
.5	.438646	83844.3	8.81395E-02	.10226
.6	.503575	105492.	8.38484E-02	9.79527E-02
.7	.559287	124488.	8.13280E-02	9.56520E-02
.8	.606318	140657.	7.98590E-02	9.45601E-02
.9	.645633	154277.	7.90263E-02	9.42082E-02 ←
1	.678448	165720.	7.86027E-02	9.43337E-02
1.1	.706053	175266.	7.84777E-02 ←	9.48065E-02
1.2	.729653	183099.	7.86016E-02	9.55663E-02
1.3	.750256	189388.	7.89421E-02	9.65737E-02
1.4	.768811	194357.	7.94603E-02	9.77824E-02
1.5	.785201	198287.	8.01070E-02	9.91343E-02
1.6	.800278	201464.	8.08313E-02	.100569
1.7	.813928	204115.	8.15917E-02	.102039
1.8	.826149	206386.	8.23627E-02	.103516
1.9	.836921	208341.	8.31340E-02	.104989
2.	.84626	209998.	8.39055E-02	.10646

R	HD	A	L =	
			S(22.5)	S(21.5)
			5.27000E-07	
.1	8.28171E-02	2934.66	.270378	.298643
.2	.163969	11334.8	.169309	.192338
.3	.241899	24090.1	.133937	.154328
.4	.31526	39653.4	.116148	.135099
.5	.382992	56390.	.105886	.124084
.6	.444372	72898.2	9.96114E-02	.117504
.7	.499039	88213.	9.56985E-02	.113594
.8	.546979	101855.	9.32589E-02	.111375
.9	.58849	113744.	9.17530E-02	.110242
1	.624117	124038.	9.08398E-02	.109805 ←
1.1	.654576	132965.	9.03109E-02	.109822
1.2	.680673	140720.	9.00518E-02	.110156
1.3	.703222	147420.	9.00098E-02 ←	.110743
1.4	.722983	153127.	9.01642E-02	.111557
1.5	.740603	157895.	9.05023E-02	.112582
1.6	.756593	161808.	9.10050E-02	.113794
1.7	.771311	164993.	9.16419E-02	.115158
1.8	.784976	167604.	9.23754E-02	.116629
1.9	.797687	169791.	9.31675E-02	.118161
2.	.809461	171676.	9.39873E-02	.119718

BASIC=8201
READY

RUN
 TAU, 1/DT, N, M, D?1,400,4,9,.32

TABLE 4-B

TAU = 1
 1/DT = 400
 N = 4
 M = 9
 D = .32

NOMINAL INSTRUMENT M = 9

L = 4.37000E-07

R	HD	A	S(22.5)	S(21.5)
.1	9.74780E-02	4735.34	.108466	.115212
.2	.192276	18070.4	7.27357E-02	7.79827E-02
.3	.281957	37686.1	5.95392E-02	6.41383E-02
.4	.36454	60561.6	5.28185E-02	5.71115E-02
.5	.438646	83844.3	4.89829E-02	5.31547E-02
.6	.503575	105492.	4.66913E-02	5.08574E-02
.7	.559287	124488.	4.52922E-02	4.95294E-02
.8	.606318	140657.	4.44207E-02	4.87810E-02
.9	.645633	154277.	4.38653E-02	4.83838E-02
1	.678448	165720.	4.35118E-02	4.82124E-02
1.1	.706053	175266.	4.33075E-02	4.82078E-02
1.2	.729653	183099.	4.32311E-02	4.83447E-02
1.3	.750256	189388.	4.32686E-02	4.86069E-02
1.4	.768611	194357.	4.34011E-02	4.89729E-02
1.5	.785201	198287.	4.36026E-02	4.94137E-02
1.6	.800278	201464.	4.38455E-02	4.98989E-02
1.7	.813928	204115.	4.41068E-02	5.04035E-02
1.8	.826149	206386.	4.43720E-02	5.09122E-02
1.9	.836921	208341.	4.46348E-02	5.14187E-02
2.	.84626	209998.	4.48947E-02	5.19234E-02

L = 5.27000E-07

R	HD	A	S(22.5)	S(21.5)
.1	8.28171E-02	2934.66	.134844	.143986
.2	.163969	11334.8	8.90206E-02	9.61489E-02
.3	.241899	24090.1	7.20444E-02	7.82432E-02
.4	.31526	39653.4	6.32181E-02	6.89285E-02
.5	.382992	56390.	5.80049E-02	6.34655E-02
.6	.444372	72898.2	5.47496E-02	6.01101E-02
.7	.499039	88213.	5.26676E-02	5.80301E-02
.8	.546979	101855.	5.13197E-02	5.67562E-02
.9	.58849	113744.	5.04347E-02	5.59961E-02
1	.624117	124038.	4.98398E-02	5.55618E-02
1.1	.654576	132965.	4.94308E-02	5.53377E-02
1.2	.680673	140720.	4.91521E-02	5.52616E-02
1.3	.703222	147420.	4.89806E-02	5.53061E-02
1.4	.722983	153127.	4.89092E-02	5.54622E-02
1.5	.740603	157895.	4.89342E-02	5.57245E-02
1.6	.756593	161808.	4.90469E-02	5.60831E-02
1.7	.771311	164993.	4.92320E-02	5.65204E-02
1.8	.784976	167604.	4.94693E-02	5.70141E-02
1.9	.797687	169791.	4.97384E-02	5.75414E-02
2.	.809461	171676.	5.00220E-02	5.80835E-02

BASIC=8201
 READY

RUN
 TAU, 1/DT, N, M, D?1,400,4,11,.32

TABLE 4-C

TAU = 1
 1/DT = 400
 N = 4
 M = 11
 D = .32

NOMINAL INSTRUMENT M = 11

L = 4.37000E-07

R	HO	A	S(22.5)	S(21.5)
.1	9.74780E-02	4735.34	.461027	.522128
.2	.192276	18070.4	.279977	.331467
.3	.281957	37686.1	.219427	.266069
.4	.36454	60561.6	.19042	.234623
.5	.438646	83844.3	.174652	.217869
.6	.503575	105492.	.165734	.208918
.7	.559287	124488.	.160733	.204524
.8	.606318	140657.	.158068	.20289
.9	.645633	154277.	.15683	.202953
1	.678448	165720.	.156512	.20411
1.1	.706053	175266.	.156856	.206051
1.2	.729653	183099.	.157735	.208622
1.3	.750256	189388.	.159067	.211726
1.4	.768611	194357.	.160762	.215254
1.5	.785201	198287.	.162717	.219078
1.6	.800278	201464.	.164828	.223069
1.7	.813928	204115.	.167013	.227123
1.8	.826149	206386.	.169224	.231184
1.9	.836921	208341.	.171441	.235231
2.	.84626	209998.	.173667	.239273

L = 5.27000E-07

R	HO	A	S(22.5)	S(21.5)
.1	8.28171E-02	2934.66	.597249	.676895
.2	.163969	11334.8	.356756	.424055
.3	.241899	24090.1	.275659	.336267
.4	.31526	39653.4	.235933	.292756
.5	.382992	56390.	.213493	.268302
.6	.444372	72898.2	.200057	.254037
.7	.499039	88213.	.191901	.245883
.8	.546979	101855.	.187031	.241602
.9	.58849	113744.	.184256	.239822
1	.624117	124038.	.182824	.239655
1.1	.654576	132965.	.182272	.240542
1.2	.680673	140720.	.182336	.242162
1.3	.703222	147420.	.182883	.244353
1.4	.722983	153127.	.183854	.247043
1.5	.740603	157895.	.185209	.250189
1.6	.756593	161808.	.186902	.253734
1.7	.771311	164993.	.188866	.257595
1.8	.784976	167604.	.191023	.261674
1.9	.797687	169791.	.193295	.265874
2.	.809461	171676.	.195623	.270117

BASIC=8201
 READY

RUN
TAU, 1/DT, N, M, D?1,400,4,10,.27

TABLE 4-D

DIAMETER D = 0.27 M

TAU = 1
1/DT = 400
N = 4
M = 10
D = .27

L = 4.37000E-07

R	HO	A	S(22.5)	S(21.5)
.1	8.41069E-02	3071.18	.331022	.360826
.2	.166471	11850.1	.20256	.227417
.3	.245468	25144.7	.158475	.180748
.4	.319697	41303.4	.136584	.157443
.5	.388067	58597.	.124062	.144205
.6	.449847	75563.9	.116447	.136339
.7	.504693	91221.7	.111707	.131674
.8	.552626	105106.	.108745	.129017
.9	.593989	117166.	.106901	.127641
1	.629382	127582.	.105765	.127082
1.1	.659573	136598.	.105089	.127057 ←
1.2	.685409	144403.	.104743	.127411
1.3	.707737	151112.	.104664 ←	.128072
1.4	.72733	156787.	.104827	.129009
1.5	.744835	161493.	.105213	.130199
1.6	.760749	165332.	.105792	.131607
1.7	.775411	168448.	.106525	.133186
1.8	.789013	171008.	.107362	.134879
1.9	.801635	173164.	.108261	.136634
2.	.813276	175032.	.109186	.138411

L = 5.27000E-07

R	HO	A	S(22.5)	S(21.5)
.1	7.09866E-02	1862.44	.429408	.469031
.2	.140917	7257.21	.258006	.291271
.3	.208785	15642.7	.199076	.228793
.4	.273685	26227.5	.16941	.197006
.5	.334847	38107.8	.151995	.178329
.6	.391672	50412.2	.14099	.16664
.7	.443751	62419.6	.133791	.15917
.8	.490868	73629.9	.129024	.154437
.9	.532999	83778.2	.125869	.151544
1	.570294	92800.8	.123798	.149901
1.1	.603048	100769.	.122452	.149104
1.2	.631672	107818.	.121593	.148875 ←
1.3	.65665	114082.	.121068	.149038
1.4	.678507	119662.	.120791	.14949
1.5	.697768	124615.	.120724 ←	.150183
1.6	.714925	128966.	.120851	.151097
1.7	.730419	132729.	.121166	.152226
1.8	.744612	135931.	.12166	.15356
1.9	.757787	138619.	.122313	.155074
2.	.770144	140867.	.123099	.156737

BASIC=8201
READY

RUN
TAU, 1/DT, N, M, D? .5, 400, 4, 10, .32

TABLE 4-E

TAU = .5
1/DT = 400
N = 4
M = 10
D = .32

SLIT INCLINATION = 26.565°

L = 4.37000E-07

R	HO	A	S(22.5)	S(21.5)
.1	.137391	13045.1	.138816	.150751
.2	.267689	47850.9	9.17262E-02	.101479
.3	.385013	94014.1	7.59100E-02	8.48584E-02
.4	.485584	140722.	6.87571E-02	7.75180E-02
.5	.568101	181240.	6.52640E-02	7.41832E-02
.6	.633538	213666.	6.35446E-02	7.28280E-02
.7	.684478	238826.	6.27385E-02	7.25087E-02
.8	.724231	257990.	6.24731E-02	7.28072E-02
.9	.756002	272053.	6.26063E-02	7.35595E-02
1	.782305	281875.	6.30532E-02	7.46667E-02
1.1	.804739	288633.	6.37052E-02	7.60034E-02
1.2	.824084	293636.	6.44370E-02	7.74245E-02
1.3	.840597	297907.	6.51486E-02	7.88143E-02
1.4	.854352	301949.	6.57930E-02	8.01189E-02
1.5	.865501	305829.	6.63721E-02	8.13417E-02
1.6	.874389	309367.	6.69181E-02	8.25209E-02
1.7	.881525	312301.	6.74739E-02	8.37068E-02
1.8	.887475	314411.	6.80782E-02	8.49451E-02
1.9	.892739	315617.	6.87529E-02	8.62610E-02
2.	.897673	316049.	6.94938E-02	8.76490E-02

L = 5.27000E-07

R	HO	A	S(22.5)	S(21.5)
.1	.12029	8900.11	.167965	.183072
.2	.235597	33138.6	.109149	.121499
.3	.341613	66550.1	8.91930E-02	.100415
.4	.435245	102122.	7.99027E-02	9.07371E-02
.5	.514915	134696.	7.51614E-02	8.60310E-02
.6	.580579	162078.	7.26818E-02	8.38448E-02
.7	.633478	184382.	7.13639E-02	8.29743E-02
.8	.675705	202579.	7.06597E-02	8.28056E-02
.9	.7097	217403.	7.03454E-02	8.30810E-02
1	.737782	229127.	7.03639E-02	8.37321E-02
1.1	.76181	237912.	7.06965E-02	8.47368E-02
1.2	.783029	244171.	7.12916E-02	8.60359E-02
1.3	.802081	248609.	7.20562E-02	8.75227E-02
1.4	.819154	251996.	7.28854E-02	8.90761E-02
1.5	.834188	254929.	7.36963E-02	9.06002E-02
1.6	.847078	257737.	7.44438E-02	9.20434E-02
1.7	.857823	260524.	7.51176E-02	9.33949E-02
1.8	.866586	263251.	7.57315E-02	9.46710E-02
1.9	.873683	265811.	7.63120E-02	9.59028E-02
2.	.879517	268064.	7.68912E-02	9.71278E-02

BASIC=8201
READY

RUN
 TAU, 1/DT, N, M, D?1,400,8,10,.32

TABLE 4-F

NUMBER OF SLITS N = 8

TAU = 1
 1/DT = 400
 N = 8
 M = 10
 D = .32

L = 4.37000E-07

R	HD	A	S(22.5)	S(21.5)
.1	9.74780E-02	4735.34	.160512	.187842
.2	.192276	18070.4	.104142	.125838
.3	.281957	37686.1	8.42633E-02	.103389
.4	.36454	60561.6	7.44715E-02	9.23239E-02
.5	.438646	83844.3	6.90894E-02	8.63821E-02
.6	.503575	105492.	6.60547E-02	8.32310E-02
.7	.559287	124488.	6.43851E-02	8.17343E-02
.8	.606318	140657.	6.35348E-02	8.12455E-02 ←
.9	.645633	154277.	6.31846E-02	8.13776E-02
1	.678448	165720.	6.31571E-02 ←	8.19102E-02
1.1	.706053	175266.	6.33645E-02	8.27320E-02
1.2	.729653	183099.	6.37667E-02	8.37907E-02
1.3	.750256	189388.	6.43372E-02	8.50524E-02
1.4	.768611	194357.	6.50451E-02	8.64774E-02
1.5	.785201	198287.	6.58511E-02	8.80161E-02
1.6	.800278	201464.	6.67148E-02	8.96178E-02
1.7	.813928	204115.	6.76039E-02	9.12421E-02
1.8	.826149	206386.	6.84986E-02	9.28657E-02
1.9	.836921	208341.	6.93919E-02	9.44813E-02
2.	.84626	209998.	7.02847E-02	9.60919E-02

L = 5.27000E-07

R	HD	A	S(22.5)	S(21.5)
.1	8.28171E-02	2934.66	.204623	.240737
.2	.163969	11334.8	.130717	.159421
.3	.241899	24090.1	.104467	.129581
.4	.31526	39653.4	9.12124E-02	.114372
.5	.382992	56390.	8.36054E-02	.105712
.6	.444372	72898.2	7.90310E-02	.100652
.7	.499039	88213.	7.62738E-02	9.77915E-02
.8	.546979	101855.	7.46629E-02	9.63419E-02
.9	.58849	113744.	7.37856E-02	9.58071E-02 ←
1	.624117	124038.	7.33778E-02	9.58624E-02
1.1	.654576	132965.	7.32755E-02 ←	9.63020E-02
1.2	.680673	140720.	7.33873E-02	9.70087E-02
1.3	.703222	147420.	7.36701E-02	9.79262E-02
1.4	.722983	153127.	7.41069E-02	9.90314E-02
1.5	.740603	157895.	7.46869E-02	.10031
1.6	.756593	161808.	7.53947E-02	.101743
1.7	.771311	164993.	7.62058E-02	.103298
1.8	.784976	167604.	7.70901E-02	.104938
1.9	.797687	169791.	7.80174E-02	.106623
2.	.809461	171676.	7.89631E-02	.108323

BASIC=8201
 READY

RUN
TAU, 1/DT, N, M, D?1,600,4,10,.32

TABLE 4-G

SAMPLING RATE = 600 Hz

TAU = 1
1/DT = 600
N = 4
M = 10
D = .32

L = 4.37000E-07

R	HO	A	S(22.5)	S(21.5)
.1	.101537	5452.55	.199938	.219644
.2	.199995	20674.9	.128149	.144164
.3	.292595	42684.1	.103317	.117656
.4	.377118	67709.7	9.12833E-02	.104862
.5	.452082	92387.	8.47688E-02	9.81105E-02
.6	.516825	114564.	8.11271E-02	9.45661E-02
.7	.571473	133461.	7.90864E-02	9.28401E-02
.8	.616818	149279.	7.79401E-02	9.21451E-02
.9	.654125	162594.	7.72941E-02	9.20319E-02 ←
1	.684908	173885.	7.69603E-02	9.22801E-02
1.1	.710705	183374.	7.68770E-02 ←	9.28142E-02
1.2	.732889	191134.	7.70342E-02	9.36203E-02
1.3	.752542	197269.	7.74190E-02	9.46821E-02
1.4	.770396	202018.	7.79918E-02	9.59533E-02
1.5	.786846	205729.	7.86921E-02	9.73630E-02
1.6	.802013	208745.	7.94577E-02	9.88387E-02
1.7	.815842	211315.	8.02424E-02	.100328
1.8	.828207	213560.	8.10228E-02	.101807
1.9	.839006	215517.	8.17933E-02	.10327
2.	.84822	217179.	8.25577E-02	.104726

L = 5.27000E-07

R	HO	A	S(22.5)	S(21.5)
.1	8.52218E-02	3244.62	.258541	.28529
.2	.168612	12492.3	.162395	.184198
.3	.248465	26414.6	.128853	.148202
.4	.323315	43185.1	.112112	.130158
.5	.392025	60919.5	.102581	.119987
.6	.453847	78067.8	9.68698E-02	.114067
.7	.508438	93645.2	9.34071E-02	.110694
.8	.555851	107260.	9.13218E-02	.108904
.9	.596482	118972.	9.00791E-02	.108096
1	.630995	129069.	8.93430E-02	.107885 ←
1.1	.660234	137862.	8.89180E-02	.108039
1.2	.685125	145558.	8.87110E-02	.108448
1.3	.706585	152244.	8.86939E-02 ←	.109073
1.4	.725443	157935.	8.88667E-02	.109915
1.5	.742391	162651.	8.92294E-02	.110972
1.6	.757944	166471.	8.97653E-02	.112224
1.7	.772439	169541.	9.04403E-02	.113632
1.8	.786053	172041.	9.12098E-02	.115142
1.9	.79883	174144.	9.20304E-02	.116702
2.	.810725	175980.	9.28686E-02	.118274

BASIC=8201
READY

Table 5. The single-slit response function $h(\eta)$ used in simulations. $\tau = 1.0$, $\lambda = 527$ nm, $r = 1.0^\circ$, $\Delta t = 1/400$ s, $D = 0.32$ m.

N.B.: $h(-\eta) = h(\eta)$

η ["]	$h(\eta)$ [-]	η ["]	$h(\eta)$ [-]
0	.624117	1.025	.118938
2.50000E-02	.62347	1.05	.112466
5.00000E-02	.621533	1.075	.106524
7.50000E-02	.618313	1.1	.101063
.1	.613825	1.125	9.60357E-02
.125	.608089	1.15	9.13941E-02
.15	.60113	1.175	8.70927E-02
.175	.59298	1.2	8.30887E-02
.2	.583677	1.225	7.93426E-02
.225	.573266	1.25	7.58188E-02
.25	.561797	1.275	7.24864E-02
.275	.54933	1.3	6.93187E-02
.3	.535926	1.325	6.62938E-02
.325	.521659	1.35	6.33943E-02
.35	.506605	1.375	6.06071E-02
.375	.490847	1.4	5.79233E-02
.4	.474472	1.425	5.53374E-02
.425	.457575	1.45	5.28470E-02
.45	.440252	1.475	5.04519E-02
.475	.422603	1.5	4.81545E-02
.5	.40473	1.525	4.59575E-02
.525	.386736	1.55	4.38651E-02
.55	.368724	1.575	4.18813E-02
.575	.350793	1.6	4.00097E-02
.6	.333042	1.625	3.82532E-02
.625	.315564	1.65	3.66138E-02
.65	.298448	1.675	3.50917E-02
.675	.281775	1.7	3.36859E-02
.7	.265619	1.725	3.23937E-02
.725	.250045	1.75	3.12108E-02
.75	.235109	1.775	3.01312E-02
.774999	.220858	1.8	2.91481E-02
.799999	.207327	1.825	2.82529E-02
.824999	.194542	1.85	2.74365E-02
.849999	.182517	1.875	2.66892E-02
.874999	.171258	1.9	2.60011E-02
.899999	.16076	1.925	2.53621E-02
.924999	.151009	1.95	2.47626E-02
.949999	.141984	1.975	2.41935E-02
.974999	.133654	2.	2.36467E-02
.999999	.125986		

Figure 1. Slit system used in numerical simulations.

$$Q_k = n_{k-100} + n_{k-90} + n_{k-60} + n_{k-40} \quad (2.1)$$

$$q_k = n_k + n_{k-10} + n_{k-30} + n_{k-50} + n_{k-70} + n_{k-80} + n_{k-120} + n_{k-140} + n_{k-150} \quad (2.2)$$

$$R_k = 12(9Q_{k-4} - 4q_{k-4}) + 9[(9Q_{k-5} - 4q_{k-5}) + (9Q_{k-3} - 4q_{k-3})] + 5[(9Q_{k-6} - 4q_{k-6}) + (9Q_{k-2} - 4q_{k-2})] + 2[(9Q_{k-7} - 4q_{k-7}) + (9Q_{k-1} - 4q_{k-1})] + [(9Q_{k-8} - 4q_{k-8}) + (9Q_k - 4q_k)] \quad (2.3)$$

If $R_k > 4000$ and $R_{k-1} < R_k \leq R_{k+1}$ then

$$\hat{p} = \left[\frac{(R_{k+1} - R_{k-1})/2}{2R_k - R_{k-1} - R_{k+1}} + k - 104 \right] u \quad (2.4)$$

Figure 2. Algorithm for determination of $\hat{p}$.

Figure 3. Example of simulation outputs: raw filter (Q_k), balanced filter ($9Q_k - 4q_k$), and smoothed filter (R_k).

Figure 4. Distribution of estimation error from 100 experiments.

Figure 5. Proposed configuration of Star Mapper slits ($D = 0.32$)
(see also Fig. 1 for details).

Figure 6. Proposed arrangement of PMT's. b_1 and v_1 are the operating tubes, while b_2 , v_2 are redundant.